

Deliverable D10.1 Model description and snapshot

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Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1	23.04.2026	Tiago Lubiana	Initial draft, including links, 2 figures and 1 table. Data still not published in Zenodo. Bibliography to be added. Reviews/suggestions of any kind are welcome.
v1	26.06.2026	Tiago Lubiana, Josh Moore	Added DOI for the data snapshot, addressed suggestions, fixed references.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIA	BioImage Archive
Bioschemas	Bioschemas community profiles for life-sciences metadata
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
IDR	Image Data Resource
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
NCBITaxon	NCBI organismal classification (NCBI Taxonomy)
NGFF	Next-generation file format
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the harmonized metadata for the foundingGIDE project, collecting study-level metadata of the major bioimaging data resources – BIA, IDR, and SSBD. The RO-Crate framework was chosen as the common base for the joint data model, for its large tooling ecosystem and compatibility with state-of-the-art semantic web standards. Building upon "Deliverable D6.1: Report in metadata model overlap and gaps", we developed a specification of a detached RO-Crate 1.2 profile describing an extensible framework, balancing expressiveness and ease of use, detailed in D7.1. Metadata from the three repositories was converted into the common format by custom pipelines and validated programmatically; the process was repeated iteratively, improving the quality of both the original metadata sources and of this deliverable.

As an archive and reuse strategy, we provide the metadata for 1584 entries representing individual studies in each of the bioimaging data resources as individual JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD) documents, as well as a joint output serialized as RDF (<https://zenodo.org/records/20922775>). We also provide a SHACL file specifying the data model in a machine-readable format, enabling validation pipelines. Finally, we enriched the deliverable with terms from the NCBI Taxonomy Ontology and the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi), improving the structure for complex searches. An example set of such complex SPARQL queries and source code for running them on the dataset is also provided.

1. Introduction

The foundingGIDE project works towards a global data-sharing framework for bioimaging, combining multiple community and technical sub-projects. At the center of this work are the metadata and the data themselves. This deliverable is the outcome of both a technical pipeline and a coordination effort, aligning bioimaging infrastructures that were developed independently across multiple continents.

Serving the biomedical community through APIs and web portals requires high-quality metadata. Harmonizing multiple resources means reaching a baseline agreement between stakeholders on formats, standards, and ontologies. It also means developer time to build pipelines that extract the internal representations of each resource and transform them into a shared framework. Quality control, validation of the outputs, and refinement of the original sources are part of the process as well.

The metadata snapshot in this deliverable follows current best practices for linked open data, while keeping the format approachable for reusers. It builds on the RO-Crate framework, which itself builds on the schema.org vocabulary and the JSON-LD standard. The deliverable shows how a heterogeneous set of biomedical databases can be integrated in practice: a single, tangible object that can be validated, loaded, and explored independently, representing the joint state of SSBDB, IDR, and the BioImage Archive in 2026. It is built with FAIR principles at its core and is ready to be a reference dataset for bioimage metadata.

2. Description of work

This snapshot builds upon the technical groundwork on model comparison done in "Deliverable D6.1: Report in metadata model overlap and gaps". The data model, materialized as a human-readable markdown file and a machine-readable SHACL description, represents the convergence of several conversations over two years, balancing trade-offs to reach a workable design across heterogeneous stakeholders. Effective communication channels played a key role: monthly Biostream meetings spanning East Asia, South America and Europe; asynchronous communication via Slack; and management via GitHub. The data model was also built with future reuse and adoption by other stakeholders in mind, being largely compatible with metadata frameworks used by generalist repositories like Dryad and Zenodo, paving the way for further integrations.

Weighing the different options, the team converged on the choice of an external lightweight framework (RO-Crate) for all the partners to conform to, and GitHub as a pragmatic platform to manage the open-source code and the open metadata. The OME-NGFF Challenge in 2024, which generated 500 TB of data in the OME-Zarr format, used a preliminary RO-Crate profile that prototyped the use of RO-Crates, as well as two resources for identifiers (FBbi for imaging methods and NCBITaxon for species).

An extended description of the processes and products related to this work is detailed in Deliverable D7.1. In particular, section 1.3 of D7.1 contextualizes the multiple technical foundingGIDE deliverables, section 2 details the rationale for the choice of RO-Crate and section 3 explains the GIDE RO-Crate Profile at depth. In this data deliverable, we provide a summary of the work as a context for the snapshot.

2.1. Technical structure overview

The RO-Crate standard was chosen as a base, as it is flexible, extensible, and widely used. The standard builds upon JSON-LD to specify metadata for research objects, with simple constraints for interoperability. Beyond a good specification, RO-Crate benefits from a living community, with multiple tools, use cases and discussion forums. Together, these factors lead to improved FAIRness of the deliverable compared to building it from scratch.

In particular, version 1.2 of the RO-Crate specification detailed the "detached RO-Crate" concept, decoupling the lightweight metadata files from the data-heavy payloads in the bioimaging repositories. It also sets the guidelines for building an RO-Crate profile, providing a layer of domain-specific rules on top of the base specification that enables additional interoperability.

The ability to separate metadata and specify a profile allowed for a strategy where each stakeholder would generate profile-conformant metadata independently, followed by a harvesting step for deployment in applications such as SPARQL endpoints, ingestion in APIs or downloadable data snapshots. In particular, a standard based on JSON-LD serves the needs of both reusers familiar with JSON and for semantic web practitioners.

2.2. The GIDE RO-Crate profile

The GIDE RO-Crate profile is a metadata model built upon the schema.org framework wherever possible, drawing on terms from Bioschemas and Darwin Core for more specific biological needs. RO-Crate is built on schema.org, as are other specifications for research datasets, including those in Zenodo and Dryad and indexed by Google Dataset Search.

Figure 1. The recommended and mandatory subset of the GIDE RO-Crate Profile. This simplified diagram highlights the core parts of the data, a common subset for IDR, SSBID and BIA. The datasets were annotated with schema.org properties. Properties linked to literal values or simple URLs are listed inside the "Dataset" box, including which repository the data comes from ("publisher"). The properties "about" and "measurementMethod" link, minimally, to terms describing the taxa under study and the imaging technique used. The concepts in black are critical for basic interoperability (MUSTs); those in lighter color are strong recommendations (SHOULDs) for compliant datasets. An extended description of the GIDE RO-Crate Profile is available in the D7.1 deliverable.

At minimum, each foundingGIDE dataset MUST be linked to descriptor concepts through the schema.org about and measurementMethod properties. They connect the individual studies with, respectively, the taxonomic identifications of the samples and the image acquisition methods for the study. We also added that the terms SHOULD come from the NCBI Taxonomy and FBbi ontology, respectively. This ensures a basic layer of semantic search across datasets.

The profile also has a longer specification, aligned closely with the REMBI model. It allows metadata to express more complex relations between a study, its biosamples and the methods used, when needed. It also allows other ontologies to be used for adding information in a free, but FAIR, format, supporting, for example, the export of Gene Ontology annotations from SSBD. The profile also allows metadata entries to be enriched with descriptive properties, including labels, descriptions, thumbnail URLs, funder information and similar, as detailed in Figure 1. As mentioned previously, details on the GIDE RO-Crate profile are provided in the D7.1 deliverable.

Notably, the profile covers contextual metadata about the whole studies, and does not provide direct means of programmatically downloading individual files. It can, however, be extended in the future, covering links from studies to direct data points. File-level access metadata will become most useful once formats and data access protocols are standardized, for example with the wide adoption of OME-Zarr by imaging repositories.

2.3 The data integration process

Each of the 3 bioimage data repositories considered in this project (SSBD, IDR and BIA) developed custom pipelines for metadata processing, outputting RO-Crate metadata in GitHub repositories:

- <https://github.com/BioImage-Archive/gide-ro-crate>
- https://github.com/German-BioImaging/idr_study_crates
- <https://github.com/opensbd/gide-ro-crate>

Metadata was harvested from these repositories and validated through a series of steps, improving the quality of the final output in a joint repository:

- <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-data-deliverable>

The overall pipeline is detailed in Figure 2.

B SHACL quality control dashboard

1577 TOTAL CRATES 0 FULLY CLEAN 311 VIOLATIONS (MUST) 4058 WARNINGS (SHOULD) 5401 INFO (MAY) 0 ERRORS

Summary by publisher

Publisher	Crates	Violations	Warnings	Info
BioImage Archive	884	0	678	3415
Image Data Resource	138	0	1661	684
SSBDdatabase	264	107	1129	654
SSBDrepository	371	204	590	648

Property coverage across crates

Level	Constraint	Have it	%	Coverage	BioImage Archiv	Image Data Reso	SSBDdatabase	SSBDrepository
Violation	Dataset MUST have at least one dwo:measurementMethod	1283/1577	81%	<div style="width: 81%;"></div>	100%	100%	68%	49%
Violation	DefinedTerm MUST have exactly one schemaName	1572/1577	100%	<div style="width: 100%;"></div>	100%	100%	100%	99%

C ontology quality control dashboard

FBbi & NCBITaxon — Ontology Term Usage Report

Generated 2026-03-30 17:38 UTC

1579 CRATES SCANNED 1665 TERM USAGES 556 EXACT MATCHES 9 CASE MISMATCHES 151 NAME MISMATCHES

0 NOT IN ONTOLOGY 949 NO NAME IN CRATE 737 CRATES WITH ISSUES

Mismatched terms across all crates

Name mismatch: Crate label differs from ontology. Case mismatch: Differs only in letter case. No name in crate: Term referenced but no name given in crate. Not in ontology: Term ID not found in the source ontology file.

Ontology: All FBbi NCBITaxon Search term ID or name...

Term ID	Ontology	Canonical label	Worst	Crates	Details
FBbi_00000256	FBbi	electron microscopy	Name mismatch	27	Name mismatch: 225-Seiriki-WhoLeBrainDev-ro-crate-metadata.json: "block-face serial microscopy tomography (PAST)" Name mismatch: 242-Wazawa-CeLLDyn-ro-

Figure 2. The metadata path to the D10.1 deliverable. A) Metadata about the studies flowed from the original repositories through a pipeline of standardization, harvesting and validation. B) SHACL validation report showing property coverage and conformance across all RO-Crates, used to identify missing or malformed metadata. C) Ontology term validation report checking consistency of NCBI Taxonomy and FBbi identifiers and labels against source ontologies. D) Sparnatural visual query interface enabling faceted exploration of the combined metadata by taxon, imaging method, and other properties. A sample of 10 results of this query is seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of a SPARQL query on the joint metadata

?study	?imagingMethod	?imagingMethodLabel	?species	?speciesLabel
idr:idr0065/	fbbi:00000247	phase contrast microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
idr:idr0091/	fbbi:00000247	phase contrast microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
idr:idr0095/	fbbi:00000246	fluorescence microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
ssbd_d:5-Koganezawa-Cell Dyn	fbbi:00000249	time lapse microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
ssbd_r:ssbd-repos-000255/	fbbi:00000249	time lapse microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
bia:S-BIAD1002	fbbi:00000246	fluorescence microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
bia:S-BIAD1002	fbbi:00000247	phase contrast microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
bia:S-BIAD1158	fbbi:00000246	fluorescence microscopy	ncbi:287	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
bia:S-BIAD1260	fbbi:00000246	fluorescence microscopy	ncbi:562	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
bia:S-BIAD1292	fbbi:00000251	confocal microscopy	ncbi:1126	<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i>

Column header represent the variables defined the SPARQL queries, e.g., “?species” in:

```

SELECT DISTINCT ?studyName, ?identifier, ?species, ?imagingMethod
WHERE ?study a schema:Dataset ;
      schema:name ?studyName ;
      schema:identifier ?identifier ;
      schema:about ?species ;
      dwc:measurementMethod ?imagingMethod .
  
```

SPARQL queries use colon-separated prefixes to abbreviate long identifiers, making the queries more compact and easier for humans to understand.: idr = <https://idr.openmicroscopy.org/study/>; ssbd_d = <https://ssbd.riken.jp/database/project/>; ssbd_r = <https://ssbd.riken.jp/repository/>; bia =

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/bioimages/studies/>; fbfi = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FBbi> ;
ncbi = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon>

2.4 The D10.1 Deliverable

The data for the D10.1 deliverable is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/20922775> and consists of the following files:

gide_profile.md: The specification of the RO-Crate profile, designed with a focus on clarity and human readability.

gide_profile_shacl_shape.ttl: A machine-readable version of the GIDE RO-Crate profile, against which the RO-Crates were validated.

gide_profile_validation.html: An HTML web page containing a snapshot of the SHACL validation. It allowed for visual exploration of inconsistencies and supported a feedback cycle that iteratively improved the quality of the deliverable.

gide_ncbi_and_fbfi_validation.html: An HTML web page containing a snapshot of a custom validation of the ontology terms used in the RO-Crates. It checks the consistency of identifiers and labels in the metadata against the reference values in the ontologies, flagging potential inconsistencies. It was also used in the feedback cycles.

gide_metadata_combined.ttl: The contents of the RO-Crates, parsed in Python with rdflib and combined into a single RDF graph serialized in Turtle. The pipeline ensures that (1) the RO-Crates are well-formed not only as JSON but also as true Linked Open Data, and (2) a single file of triples is available, making it easy to build applications on top — for example, loading into triplestores and running SPARQL endpoints.

gide_metadata_with_ontologies.ttl: To make the use of ontologies easier, the combined output was enriched with parent terms from the FBfi ontology and the NCBI Taxonomy. This enables deterministic searches using the ontology hierarchies (see Figure 2D).

The deliverable also includes files meant to facilitate exploration of the dataset:

gide_sparnatural_template.ttl: A SHACL file compatible with the Sparnatural visual query interface, describing a simplified schema for the data, with tooltips and Font Awesome icons.

Qleverfile: Configuration file for setting up a local SPARQL endpoint using QLever.

Qleverfile-ui.yml: Configuration file for a QLever-compatible local user interface for SPARQL queries, containing multiple examples for exploring the dataset (including the query in Figure 2D and Table 1).

3. Conclusion

The files in this deliverable represent a snapshot of the current metadata for GIDE, spanning entries from BIA, SSBd and IDR. The use of FAIR principles is at its core, making the outputs of GIDE readily available both for auditing and reuse, and future updates straightforward. We envision this resource

as a technical entry point for organizations intending on joining the GIDE effort in the future, and a demonstration of the value of harmonisation pipelines towards a global image data ecosystem.

References

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